

On the Nature of Addition Compounds of *ortho*-Chlorophenoxy Derivatives of Titanium(IV) with Amides

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A survey of literature reveals that metal aryloxides are increasingly finding applications as polymerisation catalysts, antioxidants, insecticides and fungicides etc.¹. However, much recent interest has been focussed upon the synthesis of substituted phenoxy derivatives of metals due to the fact that the introduction of electron-withdrawing or electron-donating groups in the phenyl ring of phenol may significantly affect the formation and stability of the corresponding substituted phenoxy derivatives of metals. In an earlier communication², we reported the synthesis and characterisation of *ortho*-chlorophenoxy derivatives of titanium(IV) of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl-o)_nCl_{4-n}$ ($n=1\rightarrow 4$). Reactivity of these phenoxides with hydroxy ligands containing labile protons has also been explored³. As a part

of our ongoing studies on their reactivity, we now report the result of a study on the acceptor strength of chlorophenoxides of titanium(IV) by reacting them with amides.

Results and Discussion

Treatment of chlorophenoxy derivatives of titanium(IV) viz. $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl)_3$, $TiCl_2(OC_6H_4Cl)_2$ and $TiCl_3(OC_6H_4Cl)$ with *N*-methylacetamide (NMA), *N,N'*-dimethylacetamide (DMA), *N*-methylformamide (NMF) and *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF) afforded the formation of addition compounds of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_nCl_{4-n} \cdot 2$ amide ($n=1\rightarrow 3$). However, the reaction of $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_4$ with amides led to the formation of an oily liquid with no definite stoichiometry. The

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elemental analyses of the isolated adducts agreed well with the proposed stoichiometry (Table 1). These compounds are moisture-sensitive but stable in dry atmosphere. They are soluble in common organic solvents. Molar conductance values of these compounds suggest their non-ionic nature. Cryoscopic molecular weights of the compounds suggest them to exist as monomers.

In the ir spectra of the compounds the appearance of carbonyl absorptions at significantly lower positions than those of the free amides generally observed at 1 685, 1 670, 1 680 and 1 660 cm^{-1} for NMF, NMA, DMF and DMA respectively, indicates that amides are coordinated through carbonyl oxygen. This is in agreement with the earlier reports on similar compounds⁴. The trends of

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE ADDITION COMPOUNDS

Compd. (Colour)	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)
		Ti	Cl		
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2NMF (Orange)	93	12.21 (12.00)	35.71 (35.50)	2.8	382 (400)
TiCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2DMF (Red)	118	11.35 (11.21)	33.59 (33.17)	3.1	—
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2NMA (Orange)	185	11.48 (11.21)	33.12 (33.17)	2.4	413 (428)
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2DMA (Orange)	105	10.90 (10.52)	31.68 (31.14)	3.0	438 (456)
TiCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2NMF (Yellow)	132	9.92 (9.75)	29.11 (28.86)	1.9	—
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2DMF (Orange)	145 ^d	9.64 (9.23)	27.59 (27.30)	3.4	—
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2NMA (Yellow)	102	9.81 (9.23)	27.55 (27.30)	1.9	506 (520)
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2DMA (Orange)	78 ^d	8.91 (8.75)	26.13 (25.91)	2.7	535 (548)
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2NMF (Yellow)	82	8.54 (8.21)	24.89 (24.31)	2.6	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2DMF (Red)	—	7.45 (7.84)	23.56 (23.20)	2.5	602 (612)
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2NMA (Yellow)	140	7.36 (7.84)	24.14 (23.20)	3.1	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2DMA (Yellow)	46	7.98 (7.50)	22.31 (22.18)	2.3	628 (640)

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF THE ADDITION COMPOUNDS

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	$\delta_{\text{N-C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ti-Cl}}$
NMA	1 670	1 300, 3 280 ^a	750	—	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2NMA	1 618	1 318, 3 330 ^a	768	592, 588	362
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2NMA	1 610	1 320, 3 325 ^a	772	590	358
TiCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2NMA	1 602	1 328, 3 318 ^a	765	605	365, 360
DMA	1 660	1 500	730	—	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2DMA	1 610	1 530	745	595, 590	355
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2DMA	1 602	1 540	740	592	360
TiCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2DMA	1 588	1 538	748	608	362, 358
NMF	1 685	1 400, 3 290 ^a	745	—	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2NMF	1 630	1 423, 3 342 ^a	760	590, 585	352
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2NMF	1 625	1 425, 3 360 ^a	772	610	365
TiCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2NMF	1 608	1 420, 3 325	768	600	368, 362
DMF	1 680	1 460	655	—	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₃ .2DMF	1 630	1 485	670	595, 602	358
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2DMF	1 625	1 498	678	592	360
TiCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2DMF	1 615	1 495	668	598	365, 362

^a ν_{NH} .

shifts of ν_{NH} , ν_{CN} and $\delta_{\text{N-C=O}}$ bands were the supporting evidences for adduct formation⁴⁻⁶. However, the ir spectra do not display any band at 500–520 cm^{-1} (present in the parent chlorophenoxides

of Ti^{IV} and assigned to $\text{Ti} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{Ti}$) suggesting a breakdown of the dimeric structure of the parent chlorophenoxides of titanium(IV) on adduct formation. The presence of sharp bands at 590–610 cm^{-1} is attributed to terminal $\nu_{\text{Ti-O}^4}$. Besides, the bands due to $\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$ is observed at 350–365 cm^{-1} , indicating an octahedral environment around central titanium as was reported earlier also^{4,6} (Table 2).

It may therefore be inferred that dimeric structure of the parent compounds was ruptured on adduct formation followed by coordination of the amides. Furthermore, based upon the magnitude of lowering of carbonyl stretching frequency of the amides on adduct formation the following order of acceptor strength for the chlorophenoxides of titanium(IV) may be proposed: $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}) > \text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2 > \text{TiCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_3$.

Experimental

o-Chlorophenol (A.R.) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Titanium(IV) chloride (A.R.) was distilled in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Compounds of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_n\text{Cl}_{4-n}$ ($n=1 \rightarrow 4$) were synthesised by the method reported earlier³.

Addition compounds of chlorophenoxy derivatives of titanium(IV) with different amides were

prepared by reacting benzene solution of the parent compound with a benzene solution of the ligand with stirring for 4–5 h, and allowed to stand overnight when a solid crystalline compound separated out. In some cases the products were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether. These were then filtered and dried under reduced pressure.

Titanium was estimated as titanium dioxide while chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method. Molecular weight of the adducts was determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of these compounds in nitrobenzene were measured an ELICO CM 82T conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (KBr) were scanned on Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrophotometers.

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